

INCIDENT COMMAND SYSTEM (ICS): A STANDARDISED SYSTEM FOR MANAGING EMERGENCIES AND LARGE-SCALE INCIDENTS

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Abstract: *The Incident Command System (ICS) is a widely recognized and standardized framework for managing emergencies and large-scale incidents. ICS has evolved into a comprehensive system for coordinating emergency responses across various jurisdictions and organizations. The key objectives of the research evolve the implementation of ICS in diverse emergency situations, identifying challenges faced during its application and proposing strategies to mitigate these challenges. This research will provide a comprehensive analysis of ICS’s role in improving communication and reducing misunderstandings during high-stress incidents, thereby offering valuable insights into its application in modern emergency management. The conclusion of the research is drawn from the importance of communication, data management, and coordination among agencies as integral elements for successful incident management.*

1.0 Introduction

The Incident Command System (ICS) represents a widely recognised and standardised structure for managing large-scale emergencies and disasters that require integrated response measures. This system was created to help simplify and improve resource organisation and communication across the different agencies

and organisations engaged in dealing with disasters, crises, and events of all sizes. The Incident Command System (ICS) responds to the rising complexity of handling incidents, particularly those involving numerous jurisdictions and different public safety, construction and security organisations (National Institute of Disaster Management,

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2023). The ICS framework promotes a clear chain of command, ensuring accountability and minimizing confusion in high-pressure environments, which is critical in situations involving multiple responding entities.

The historical development of ICS, [including its adaptation through the FIRESOPE project and the National Incident Management System (NIMS)] is focused at underlining its growth and integrating into national disaster response protocols. ICS has contributed to the standardization of incident management, particularly in improving inter-agency collaboration and ensuring efficient resource deployment. Its impact on disaster management has been significant in fostering a more organized, effective, and coordinated response to large-scale emergencies and crises.

ICS is meant to be adaptive and adaptable, making it ideal for a broad range of situations, from small regional emergencies to huge, complex, and persistent events such as catastrophes, terrorist attacks, or medical emergencies. The system offers a standardised approach to event management, enabling responders to successfully collaborate and share assets despite their agency or organisational affiliations.

1.1 Background context

One of the ICS's guiding principles is the clear chain of authority, which develops an organisational hierarchy for making decisions and resource distribution (Federal Emergency Management Agency 2023). This framework helps to eliminate misunderstanding and guarantees that all responding participants understand their roles and duties.

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Figure 1: ICS basic organisation chart

(Source: Federal Emergency Management Agency 2023)

Figure 1 illustrates the basic organisational structure of ICS which portrays the chain of command. This chain of command contains essential positions with specialised tasks and authorities, such as Operations Division Chief, Incident Commander, Planning Division Chief, Logistics Section Chief, and Finance/Administration Division Chief ((Federal Emergency Management Agency 2023). These authorities take part in mitigating the issues faced during large-scale emergencies and disasters. ICS also places a strong emphasis on good communication and data management for conveying crucial information among

responders (National Institute of Disaster Management 2023). This approach of ICS lowers the possibility of misinterpretation and misconceptions in high-stress and fast-shifting circumstances. This nature of ICS is especially important in instances where multiple organisations with different communication methods must collaborate seamlessly.

1.2 History

At the beginning of this work, despite the recognition that there were incident or field level shortfalls in organization and terminology, there was no mention of the need to develop an on the ground incident management system like ICS.

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Most of the efforts were focused on the multi-agency coordination challenges above the incident or field level. It was not until 1972 when Firefighting Resources of Southern California Organized for Potential Emergencies (FIRESCOPE) was formed that this need was recognized and the concept of ICS was first discussed. Also, ICS was originally called Field Command Operations System.^[9]

The ICS concept was formed in 1968 at a meeting of Fire Chiefs in Southern California. The program reflects the management hierarchy of the US Navy, and at first was used mainly to fight California wildfires. During the 1970s ICS was fully developed during massive wildfire suppression efforts in California (FIRESCOPE) that followed a series of catastrophic wildfires, starting with the massive Laguna fire in 1970. Property damage ran into the millions, and many people died or were injured. Studies determined that response problems often related to communication and management deficiencies rather than lack of resources or failure of tactics.^{[7][8]}

Emergency managers determined that the existing management structures – frequently unique to each agency – did not scale to dealing with massive mutual aid responses involving dozens of distinct agencies and when these various agencies worked together their specific training and procedures clashed. As a result, a new command and control paradigm was collaboratively developed to create a consistent,

integrated framework for the management of all incidents from small incidents to large, multi-agency emergencies.

ICS became a national model for command structures at a fire, crime scene or major incident. ICS was used in New York City at the first attack on the World Trade Center in 1993. On 1 March 2004, the Department of Homeland Security, in accordance with the passage of Homeland Security Presidential Directive 5 (HSPD-5) calling for a standardized approach to incident management among all federal, state, and local agencies, developed the National Incident Management System (NIMS) which integrates ICS. Additionally, it was mandated that NIMS (and thus ICS) must be used to manage emergencies to receive federal funding.

1.3 Jurisdiction and legitimacy

The Incident Command System (ICS) is a significant advancement in disaster management and response. Its relevance derives from the fact that it provides a standardised and highly efficient structure for dealing with crises and large-scale disasters. ICS simplifies the coordination of disparate authorities and organisations, providing a smooth response to crises such as catastrophic events, industrial accidents, and public health emergencies (Federal Emergency Management Agency 2023). Therefore, this work will provide probable outcomes in analysing ICS in improving communication which reduces misunderstanding in high-stress circumstances.

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ICS encourages coordination among many stakeholders, including government organisations, emergency responders, and non-governmental organisations, resulting in a coordinated response that saves lives and lowers property damage. Therefore, the probable outcomes of this work will contribute to determining the role and significance of ICS in disaster management in organisations.

2.0 Literature Review

Approach for literature search and information store to carry out a critical literature review

The literature search method will include the key words and sentences that are associated with the research topic. This will help to identify

relevant secondary qualitative articles that can provide insight to understand the significance of ICS in an organisation to address emergencies and large-scale incidents. In addition to this, the articles will be filtered by using inclusion and exclusion criteria to improve search results and obtained data will be compared and contrasted with each other to present a critical literature output. According to the view of Keung *et al.* (2020: 47-58), a research search strategy can be improved by using exclusion and exclusion criteria. Following this the collected research articles will be stored in an archived folder that can be easily accessed for individuals associated with the research.

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles present in English languages Articles since 2019 -2023 Articles with qualitative findings and outcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles present in other language than English are excluded Articles prior 2019 are excluded Articles providing quantitative values are excluded

2.1 Role of ICS in managing large-scale incidents and emergencies in Organisation.

Incident command system is a standardised, incident management concept that is used onsite within an organisation for reducing the risk of incident within an organisation. According to the view of Chang and Trainor (2020: 241-267), an

organisation implements ICS for improving their organisational structure in order to resolve the complexities of multiple incidents within an organisation. The application of ICS helps to reduce risk and helps the firm to manage risk without jurisdictional boundaries. On the other hand, Burgiel (2020: 155-165) states that for successful implementation of ICS the five

functional areas are required to be established such as command, plan, operate, logistics and administration along with financial support. These aspects help to improve the understanding and successful implementation of ICS within the organisation to control the potential risk aspects. In addition to this, the ICS is used to gain a span of controlled recommendations that is able to improve risk evaluation and monitoring systems. As per the view of Farcas et al. (2021: 31-36), an organisation is able to command, control and coordinate efficiently during an incident site. This helps to overcome the challenge of monitoring and identifying approaches to address emergencies. The ICS provides a systematic procedure and states that can be used by an organisation to evaluate on their current risk assessment techniques so that implementation of ICS can be made to ensure success large-scale risk and emergency monitoring. On the other hand, Asghar et al. (2019: 10) states that ICS is able to foster a strong communication network among the risk assessment members and provide them insights to efficiently manage work. This requires a common hierarchical system within the organisation so that systematic information sharing can be carried out to make informed decisions and improve incident management techniques within the organisation. Thus, ICS plays an important role in improving the incident and risk management approaches within an organisation.

2.2 Application of ICS for reducing impact of large-scale incidents and Emergencies.

The ICS are applied by using a successive stage plan that helps to acquire scale range in an effective way. According to the view of Hall et al. (2022: 30), ICS is a strategic approach that is primarily used by government agencies, police, fire and safety departments during complicated situations. Thus results in improving the filed response system and understanding the risk parameters so that precautionary measures can be taken appropriately. On the other hand, Bahrami et al. (2020: 62) state that ICS are also used to improve integrated risk management systems. This helps to develop strategies based on the phase of mitigation, response, preparedness and recover from a large-scale incident and emergencies.

In addition to this, the impact of applying ICs on organisation brings insight to understand the various hazards that can be cured such as medical, fire or natural hazards. As per the view of Elmhadhbi et al. (2020: 3887-3901), the ICS implementation helps to identify a series of actions as an emergency management program in response to various risk circumstances. The risk analysis and management technique used in ICS is developed on the basis of hazard vulnerability analysis and their likelihood of occurrences. On the other hand, Thielsch et al. (2021: 150-187) state that ICS is able to provide an extended understanding of simple to complex

emergencies and perform on different levels. ICS provides a common language for the emergency responders so that quick actions and chance of false actions can be reduced. Thus, the application of ICS has a positive impact on improving the overall risk management system by using a chain of command to address large scale risks and emergencies.

2.3 Challenges to implement incident command system in an Organisation.

The implementation of an incident command system within an organisation can become difficult due to the advanced technologies and operating approach. According to the view of Rubens (2023: 85), ICS lacks in providing a strong understanding of operating technology and information technology convergence due to which managing cyber-attacks within an organisation can become difficult. In addition to this, challenges can be experienced to develop an asset inventory that is needed for managing and implementing ICS. On the other hand, Yaacoub et al. (2020: 103201) states that financial limitations can create challenges to develop network baseline and secure remote access to control ICS devices. These limitations can affect the effectiveness and implementation practices of ICS within an organisation.

In addition to this, an organisation can also experience regulatory, compliance and change management challenges within an organisation. As stated by Alqudah et al. (2022: 100177), lack of strong regulatory and change management

systems can result in creating employee resistance to change. This can result in affecting the ICS implementation within the organisation. On the other hand Chen et al. (2020: 1487-1497), states that an organisation needs to engage with practices that help to achieve operational safety, system availability and legacy architecture to provide strategic support for ICS implementation. However, lacking operational safety, system availability can lead to a challenge in effective implementation of ICS for large scale risk and emergency management. Thus, it is important to critically evaluate on the impact of ICS and analysing the various challenges that are associated with ICS practices to ensure successful implementation of ICS within the organisation.

3.0 Strategies to mitigate challenges related to implementation of ICS system COSO ERM framework

The COSO ERM framework is a framework that can be adopted by an organisation to improve their understanding of risk management and prioritise risks. According to the view of Shad et al. (2019: 415-425), COSO ERM framework helps to improve business performances by introducing a risk management framework to manage business risk. The COSO ERM framework has five distinct components that are used to improve risk monitoring ability such as control environment, risk assessment, information, monitoring activities, communication and existing control devices.

These aspects are used together to evaluate the existing risk monitoring and managing practices within the organisation so that the effect of ICS can be increased. Furthermore, the COSO framework also helps to improve internal control operation which is essential to increase the effectiveness of ICS implementation. Thus, the COSO ERM framework is effective in terms of resolving the implementation challenges of ICS within an organisation.

3.1 Major Concepts of ICS

3.1.1 Chain of Command

In ICS, every individual involved in the operation reports to just one supervisor. This prevents conflicting orders from multiple supervisors, which helps ensure clear accountability, reduce independent decision-making, streamline the flow of information, and enhance coordination and safety. This is a fundamental principle of the ICS structure. Historically, individual response agencies developed their own protocols and terminology, which could cause confusion since terms might be understood differently by each organization. To avoid misunderstandings, using common terminology is crucial when multiple organizations collaborate. The ICS encourages standardized terminology and includes a glossary to maintain consistency in position titles, resource descriptions, organizational structures, and more. Common terminology is especially vital in command roles like Incident Commander, Safety Officer, and Operations Section Chief.

3.1.2 Goal-Oriented ICS Management

Incidents are managed by setting specific objectives, ranked by priority, that are achievable within a given timeframe. These objectives are accomplished by creating strategies (well detailed action plans) and then determining ways (specific methods for implementing the strategies).

3.1.3 Flexible and Modular Organization

The ICS structure is designed to expand or contract based on the scope, resources, and hazards of the incident. The command is initially set up from the top down, with only the most critical roles filled first. As the incident scales, more roles are added as necessary. Conversely, as the incident diminishes, roles are consolidated. This flexibility allows for an adaptable response tailored to the situation's size and complexity.

3.1.4 Span of Management

The ICS ensures that the number of individuals one supervisor manages does not exceed seven, with five being the ideal number. If a supervisor is managing more than seven, the structure needs to expand to delegate responsibilities. Conversely, fewer than three individuals may indicate that the position's authority could be absorbed by the next higher level in the command sequence

3.2 Coordination of ICS

ICS allows organizations to coordinate efforts, even when they don't frequently work together. The system's flexibility helps integrate different

organizations, but managing such a diverse network can be challenging. Strong pre-existing relationships among responders generally lead to better coordination, while contested authority or highly diverse networks can hinder effective collaboration.

3.2.1 Incident Action Plans (IAPs)

IAPs provide clarity and cohesion by setting specific, measurable objectives for each operational period (typically 12 hours). They detail what needs to be done, who is responsible, how communication will occur, and procedures for handling injuries. IAPs help to prevent confusion and ensure coordinated action.

3.2.2 Comprehensive Resource Management

This principle emphasizes tracking all resources and personnel during an incident. It involves categorizing, ordering, dispatching, tracking, and recovering resources to ensure they are used efficiently and demobilized properly. T-Cards are commonly used to manage resource statuses in a visual and systematic way.

3.3 Integrated Communications

ICS requires an integrated communication system, including voice and data equipment, planning, and protocols. This ensures seamless internal and external communication, helping to maintain the flow of information throughout the response efforts.

3.3.1 Command Transfer

Command can be transferred during an incident for various reasons, such as the need for a more

qualified individual to manage an expanding situation or when the incident scales down, and a less qualified person can handle the command. This process always involves a formal briefing, whether oral, written, or a combination of both.

3.3.2 Facilities

ICS facilities include the Incident Command Post (ICP), Staging Areas, Bases, Camps, Helibases, and Helispots, each serving a specific purpose to support operations. These facilities must be planned and designated before an incident, with each fulfilling different logistical or administrative needs.

3.3.3 Equipment Nomenclature

ICS uses specific terms to categorize and describe equipment, such as tankers, tenders, and vehicles. This helps ensure consistency and clarity when resources are deployed and managed.

3.3.4 ICS Structure

The ICS structure operates across various levels (Tier 1, Tier2, and Tier3), with each level designed for incidents of varying complexity.

- **Tier1- Level ICS** focuses on small-scale incidents.
- **Tier2-Level ICS** introduces multi-agency involvement and operational periods
- **Tier3-Level ICS** deals with large, complex incidents involving multiple agencies and coordination of resources across numerous areas

3.4 Wider resource management

Wider and broader resource management is a key management principle that implies that all assets and personnel during an event need to be tracked and accounted for. It can also include processes for reimbursement for resources, as appropriate. Resource management includes processes for: ^[6]

- Categorizing resources
- Ordering resources
- Dispatching resources
- Tracking resources
- Recovering resources

A well detailed resource management ensures that visibility is retained over all resources so they can be moved quickly to support the preparation and response to an incident and ensuring a graceful demobilization. It also applies to the classification of resources by type and kind, and the categorization of resources by their status.

- **Assigned** resources are those that are working on a field assignment under the direction of a supervisor.
- **Available** resources are those that are ready for deployment (staged) but have not been assigned to a field assignment.
- **Out-of-service** resources are those that are not in either the "available" or "assigned" categories. Resources can be "out-of-service" for a variety of reasons including resupplying after a sortie (most common), shortfall in staffing, personnel taking a rest, damaged or inoperable.

Failure of Incident Command System (ICS)

1. Lack of situational awareness: Not recognising activities within the environment has led to a waste of effort and resources

2. Inability to form a unified command: A lack of unified command is a major issue staring at ICS, particularly in large-scale incidents with the involvement of multiple agencies.

3. Poor Communication: Communication breakdown amongst the different agencies causes a communication gap.

4. Lack of Training: The inability to train the team is another failure, as most team members lack the knowledge and principles of the incident command system procedures. This has caused confusion and poor application of systems during an emergency.

4.0 Solutions to the Problems of ICS

4.1 Integrated communications

Developing an integrated voice and data communications system, including equipment, systems, and protocols, must occur before an incident.^[6]

Effective ICS communications include three elements:

- **Modes:** The "hardware" systems that transfer information.
- **Planning:** Planning for the use of all available communications resources.

- **Networks:** The procedures and processes for transferring information internally and externally.

4.2 Design an ICS Structure Personnel

ICS is structured in hierarchical levels, with each level having distinct titles (e.g., a person in charge of a section is referred to as a "chief," and the leader of a branch is called a "director"). The titles for each level of supervision are as follows:

- **Incident Commander (IC)**
- **Command Staff Member (Officer)** – Command staff
- **Section Chief** – General staff
- **Branch Director**
- **Division Supervisor** – Divisions are units based on geography or jurisdictional boundaries, not necessarily by the types of resources within them.
- **Group Supervisor** – Groups are units formed for specific purposes, based on agency lines or the resources within the group.
- **Unit, Team, or Task Force Leader** – Examples include "communications unit," "medical strike team," or a "reconnaissance task force." A strike team consists of the same resources (e.g., four ambulances), while a task force includes different resource types (e.g., one ambulance, two fire trucks, and a police car).
- **Individual Resource** – The smallest unit within ICS, usually referring to one person or a piece of equipment. It can also include

equipment with an operator or multiple people working together.

4.3 Facilities

ICS uses a standard set of facilities designed for different operational needs. These facilities are essential to the structure of the response operations and can vary widely in location and size. The key facilities should include:

- **Incident Command Post (ICP):** This is where the Incident Commander operates during the response. The ICP may be in a vehicle, trailer, tent, or building and is located outside of the hazard zone but close enough to maintain command. Every incident or event requires an ICP, which may change locations during the event.
- **Staging Area:** A designated space near the incident scene where tactical resources are stored until assigned. Staging areas must be sufficiently close for quick deployment but far enough from the impact zone for safety. Multiple staging areas may be established at an incident.
- **Base:** This is the primary location for logistics and administrative functions, typically managed by the logistics section. A base is always out-of-service and located away from the immediate hazard zone.
- **Camps:** Temporary facilities within the general incident area, providing services like food, water, sanitation, and sleeping arrangements for personnel far from the base. Camps are designated by location or number.

- **Helipad:** A location for managing helicopter operations, including fueling and maintenance. Helibases are typically used long-term.

- **Helispots:** Temporary helicopter landing zones set up at or near the incident scene.

4.4 During large or complex incidents, set up additional support facilities

Emergency Operations Center (EOC): A facility for overall command and control during a disaster, providing strategic oversight without directly managing field operations. An EOC is responsible for gathering and analysing data, making decisions to protect life and property, and ensuring continuity of operations.

- **Joint Information Center (JIC):** A facility where media representatives interact with incident staff. It supports communication between the incident and the public, often including technical assets like internet, phones, and power.

- **Joint Operations Center (JOC):** A pre-established facility where multiple agencies coordinate and interact, particularly useful for incidents involving multiple jurisdictions or agencies.

- **Multiple Agency Coordination Center (MACC):** A central facility for managing multiple incidents in a specific area, where agencies can coordinate resources, make

strategic decisions, and ensure all incidents are handled effectively.

4.6 Training

Ensure team members are trained on the usage of all equipment

5.0 Equipment

ICS uses a standardized nomenclature for equipment to ensure clarity and consistency across incidents:

- **Tanker:** An aircraft that carries fuel or water.

- **Tender/Bowser:** A ground vehicle that carries fuel, water, or fire-fighting foam.

- **Computers:** Increasingly essential for managing and sharing information, computers help responders access the latest data and coordinate efforts effectively.

5.1 Resource Type and Kind

In ICS, resources are categorized by both "type" and "kind":

- **Type:** Describes the size or capability of the resource (e.g., a 50 kW generator or a 3-ton truck).

- **Kind:** Refers to the actual resource (e.g., a generator or a truck).

For example, a request for aerial reconnaissance could be fulfilled by either a fixed-wing aircraft or a rotary-wing aircraft, depending on availability, as long as the request specifies the type and kind of resource needed.

5.2 Command Transfer

The transfer of command occurs for various

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reasons, such as when the incident grows and requires a more qualified individual to manage it, or when the incident scales down and the command can be passed to someone less experienced. Command transfer may also occur due to jurisdictional changes, personnel turnover, or an extended response. The process involves a formal briefing (oral, written, or both) to ensure a smooth transition.

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